

Deep Learning-based Joint Pilot and Data Power Control in Cell-Free Massive MIMO Networks

Nuwanthika Rajapaksha, Nandana Rajatheva, and Matti Latva-aho

Centre for Wireless Communications, University of Oulu, Finland

E-mail: {nuwanthika.rajapaksha, nandana.rajatheva, matti.latva-aho}@oulu.fi

Abstract—A deep learning (DL)-based joint pilot and data power control algorithm that solves the sum rate maximization problem in a cell-free massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) system is proposed. The sum rate optimization problem for the uplink is formulated subject to per-user total transmit energy budget constraints, where user pilot and data power allocations are optimized to maximize the system sum rate. Instead of solving the non-convex problem using mathematical optimization theory, we utilize a data-driven solution approach to learn the optimal solutions. Specifically, we model a deep neural network (DNN) and train it via unsupervised learning using a custom loss function that captures the sum rate optimization objective and transmit energy constraints in the optimization problem. This unsupervised approach has a simpler and more flexible model training stage since it does not require labeled data for model training as in supervised learning. Simulation results show that the proposed DNN-based joint pilot and data power control improves the system sum rate compared to equal power and equal energy allocation heuristics and data power control only approach. Furthermore, the joint power allocation results in significant energy savings (around 60 %) compared to fixed power allocation schemes.

Index Terms—cell-free massive MIMO, sum rate maximization, power control, deep learning, unsupervised learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Massive MIMO, where a base station with a large number of antennas simultaneously serves many users, has become a key technology in fifth-generation (5G) networks due to their high throughput and reliability [1]–[3]. Cell-free massive MIMO, introduced in [4], is a novel network architecture to overcome limitations in conventional centralized or cellular massive MIMO and to provide macro-diversity gain, inter-cell interference mitigation, and more uniform quality of service among the users. It does not have the concept of cells or cell boundaries, and a large number of access points (APs) distributed over a wide area connected to a central processing unit (CPU) via fronthaul links coherently serve a much smaller number of users [5]. Since all users in the network are served simultaneously using the same time-frequency resource, proper resource allocation such as pilot assignment, power control, user association, etc. is essential to limit multi-user interference and optimize the overall network performance. Power control is usually carried out to maximize

a utility such as minimum user rate, sum rate, or the energy efficiency of the network [5], [6]. The studies [7], [8] proposed pilot power control to minimize the mean-squared error of the channel estimation in scenarios where non-orthogonal pilots are used causing pilot contamination. The work in [9]–[11] considered joint pilot and data power control under per-user maximum transmit power and maximum total transmit energy constraints.

These radio resource allocation problems are usually solved using optimization or heuristics-based methods which consist of computationally complex algorithms with iterative processing steps. Furthermore, convex approximations of non-convex problems and heuristic methods often result in sub-optimal solutions. On the other hand, machine learning techniques can complement the traditional model-driven algorithmic design with data-driven approaches to overcome these algorithmic deficiencies. Especially, the universal function approximation property of the artificial neural networks has enabled deep learning (DL)-based techniques to be used in radio resource allocation tasks with lower complexity than traditional optimization-based approaches. Several studies have proposed DL-based power control for cellular and cell-free massive MIMO systems [6], [12]–[15]. They all used a supervised learning approach where a DNN is trained to learn the mapping between the inputs (user locations or channel statistics) and the optimal power allocations obtained by an optimization algorithm. On the other hand, the unsupervised learning power control algorithms we proposed in [16], [17] do not require labeled data for model training, hence simplifying the data preparation and model training stage. Therefore, in this work also we are interested in such an unsupervised learning approach for joint pilot and data power control to maximize the uplink sum rate of a cell-free massive MIMO network. The contributions of the paper are as follows:

- In this paper, we consider joint pilot and data power control for sum rate maximization in a cell-free massive MIMO system. To find solutions to the non-convex optimization problem, we propose a DL-based low-complexity approach to learn the power allocation outputs to maximize the system sum rate subject to per-user maximum transmit energy constraints.
- In contrast to the usually used supervised learning-based approach, we use an unsupervised learning approach to learn the power allocation outputs using large-scale

This work was supported in part by the Hexa-X-II project, funded by the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant 101095759 and in part by the Research Council of Finland (former Academy of Finland) 6G Flagship programme under Grant number 346208.

channel statistics as model inputs. It does not require labeled data for model training as in supervised learning, which makes the data preparation and model training simpler, more practical, and flexible since the DNN can be easily retrained in a changing environment over time.

- We present simulation results comparing the performance of the proposed DL-based power allocation algorithm and other optimization and heuristics-based approaches to solve the sum rate maximization problem, showing the potential of the proposed unsupervised learning-based joint power control approach.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a cell-free massive MIMO system with M single-antenna APs and K single-antenna users randomly distributed in a $D \times D$ geographic area. The APs are connected to a CPU via backhaul connections. The channel coefficient between k th user and m th AP is modeled as $g_{mk} = \sqrt{\beta_{mk}}h_{mk}$ [5]. Here, β_{mk} is the large-scale fading consisting of pathloss and shadowing, and $h_{mk} \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ represents the small-scale fading between k th user and m th AP. The uplink data transmission is considered which follows an initial uplink training phase for channel estimation.

A. Uplink Training: Pilot Transmission and Channel Estimation

First, all the users undergo an uplink training phase to estimate the uplink channel coefficients where all K users simultaneously transmit their pilot sequences of length τ symbols to the APs where $\tau < \tau_c$ for the coherence interval τ_c . Let $\sqrt{\tau\rho_k^p}\phi_k \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau \times 1}$ be the pilot sequence assigned to k th user with $\|\phi_k\|^2 = 1$ and power ρ_k^p . The received signal at m th AP is then given by

$$\mathbf{y}_{p,m} = \sqrt{\tau} \sum_{k=1}^K \sqrt{\rho_k^p} g_{mk} \phi_k + \mathbf{w}_{p,m}, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{p,m} \in \mathbb{C}^{\tau \times 1}$ is the additive noise at m th AP with i.i.d $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$ elements. Then, m th AP estimates the channel $g_{mk}, \forall k$ by projecting the received signal $\mathbf{y}_{p,m}$ onto pilot sequence ϕ_k^H as $\tilde{y}_{p,mk} = \phi_k^H \mathbf{y}_{p,m}$ [5]. Thus,

$$\tilde{y}_{p,mk} = \sqrt{\tau\rho_k^p} g_{mk} + \sum_{k' \neq 1}^K \sqrt{\tau\rho_{k'}^p} g_{mk'} \phi_k^H \phi_{k'} + \phi_k^H \mathbf{w}_{p,m}, \quad (2)$$

where the linear minimum mean-squared error (MMSE) estimate of g_{mk} given $\tilde{y}_{p,mk}$ is

$$\hat{g}_{mk} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{\tilde{y}_{p,mk}^* g_{mk}\}}{\mathbb{E}\{|\tilde{y}_{p,mk}|^2\}} \tilde{y}_{p,mk} = c_{mk} \tilde{y}_{p,mk}, \quad (3)$$

where c_{mk} is obtained as [5]

$$c_{mk} = \frac{\sqrt{\tau\rho_k^p} \beta_{mk}}{\tau \sum_{k'=1}^K \rho_{k'}^p \beta_{mk'} + |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 + 1}. \quad (4)$$

B. Uplink Data Transmission

After the training phase, the uplink data transmission begins where all the users simultaneously send their signals to the APs. Let $x_k = \sqrt{\rho_k^u} s_k$ be the transmit signal from k th user, where s_k is the transmit symbol with $\mathbb{E}\{|s_k|^2\} = 1$ and is the transmit power of user k . The received signal at m th AP from all the users is given by

$$y_m = \sum_{k=1}^K g_{mk} x_k + w_m = \sum_{k=1}^K g_{mk} \sqrt{\rho_k^u} s_k + w_m, \quad (5)$$

where $w_m \sim \mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma^2)$ is the additive noise at m th AP. Then match filtering is done at each AP using the locally obtained channel estimate \hat{g}_{mk} , and the scaled received signals are sent to the CPU for joint detection. The aggregated received signal r_k (6) at the CPU is used to detect s_k . We assume the large-scale fading β_{mk} to be known [5].

$$r_k = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k'=1}^K \sqrt{\rho_{k'}^u} \hat{g}_{mk}^* g_{mk'} s_{k'} + \sum_{m=1}^M \hat{g}_{mk}^* w_m. \quad (6)$$

C. Sum Rate Maximization via Joint Pilot and Data Power Control

We aim to maximize the system sum rate via joint pilot and uplink data power control subject to per-user energy budget constraints. We assume that only the knowledge of channel statistics is used at the CPU when deriving the achievable rate of each user. The uplink rate for the k th user can be derived as (7). There, $\gamma_{mk} = \mathbb{E}\{|\hat{g}_{mk}|^2\} = \sqrt{\tau\rho_p} \beta_{mk} c_{mk}$. The achievable rate in (7) is a function of large-scale fading coefficients β_{mk} and user transmit power coefficients ρ_k^p, ρ_k^u , and does not involve instantaneous channel values. The sum rate maximization problem can then be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} P1 : \quad & \max_{\{\rho_k^p\}, \{\rho_k^u\}} \sum_{k=1}^K R_k^u, \\ & \text{subject to} \quad \tau\rho_k^p + (\tau_c - \tau)\rho_k^u \leq E_{max}, \quad \forall k, \\ & \quad \quad \quad \rho_k^p \geq 0, \rho_k^u \geq 0, \quad \forall k, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where E_{max} is the maximum energy budget for each user for pilot and uplink data transmission in a coherence interval τ_c . The sum rate optimization problem P1 is non-convex and non-polynomial time (NP)-hard. Therefore, to solve this non-convex joint optimization problem in a data-driven manner, we propose a DL-based power control approach which is the main contribution of this work.

III. DEEP LEARNING-BASED JOINT POWER CONTROL

Our target is to learn the optimal resource allocations for each user to maximize the system sum rate without solving the computationally complex optimization problem P1. To learn the user pilot and data power allocations, we propose an unsupervised learning-based solution similar to [16] that does not require optimal ground truth outputs for model training. Specifically, a DNN is directly fed with inputs to learn the optimum solutions for minimizing a given loss

$$R_k^u = \frac{(\tau_c - \tau)}{\tau_c} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\rho_k^u \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{mk} \right)^2}{\sum_{k' \neq k}^K \rho_{k'}^u \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{mk'} \sqrt{\frac{\rho_{k'}^p \beta_{mk'}}{\rho_k^p \beta_{mk}}} \right)^2 + |\phi_k^H \phi_{k'}|^2 + \sum_{k'=1}^K \rho_{k'}^u \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{mk} \beta_{mk'} + \sigma^2 \sum_{m=1}^M \gamma_{mk}} \right). \quad (7)$$

function during training. Such an approach is more flexible and adaptable for practical implementation in a changing wireless communications environment.

To this end, we designed and implemented a feedforward DNN consisting of $L+1$ layers that are sequentially connected to produce the mapping $f(\mathbf{x}_0; \boldsymbol{\theta}) : \mathbb{R}^{N_0 \times 1} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_L \times 1}$ of an input vector $\mathbf{x}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{N_0 \times 1}$ to an output vector $\mathbf{x}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{N_L \times 1}$ through L iterative processing steps, for a set of trainable parameters set $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. Input to the network is the large-scale channel coefficients β_{mk} of all the APs and users, aligned as a column vector denoted by $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ with dimension $N_0 = MK$. Thus, the DNN input is $\mathbf{x}_0 = \boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathbb{R}^{MK \times 1}$. The model outputs the estimated power allocation vector $[\boldsymbol{\rho}^p, \boldsymbol{\rho}^u] \in \mathbb{R}_+^{2K \times 1}$, where $\boldsymbol{\rho}^p = [\rho_1^p, \rho_2^p, \dots, \rho_K^p]$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}^u = [\rho_1^u, \rho_2^u, \dots, \rho_K^u]$ are the pilot and data power allocation vectors of all K users respectively. The DNN has 5 layers ($L = 4$) and consists of two parts, to predict the pilot and data power control vectors $\boldsymbol{\rho}^p, \boldsymbol{\rho}^u$ respectively. Each part has $\{MK, M, M, M, K\}$ number of neurons in each layer where the first layer is the large-scale fading channel inputs and the last layer is the pilot/data power control vectors $\boldsymbol{\rho}^p, \boldsymbol{\rho}^u$. This simple DNN model layout enables lower training complexity and can produce outputs with a lower online complexity. Furthermore, all the hidden layers have the eLU (exponential linear unit) activation function whereas the output layer has $ReLU$ activation function to guarantee the $\rho_k^u \geq 0$ and $\rho_k^p \geq 0$ constraints.

Given that the optimization objective of problem P1 in (8) is to maximize the sum rate, we apply the following loss function for model training as

$$loss = -\mathbb{E}_{\boldsymbol{\beta}} \left[R(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\theta})_{sum} + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k ReLU(E_{k,total} - E_{max}) \right], \quad (9)$$

where $R(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\theta})_{sum} = \sum_{k=1}^K R(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\theta})_k^u$ is the sum rate of all the K users for a given channel realization with large-scale fading $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and given $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. For each user k , $R(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\theta})_k^u$ is calculated from (7) using the large-scale channel coefficients $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ and the DNN power allocation outputs $\rho^p(\boldsymbol{\theta}), \rho^u(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ for a given set of trainable parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The total energy of user k for pilot and data transmission for a given DNN output $[\boldsymbol{\rho}^p, \boldsymbol{\rho}^u]$ is denoted by $E_{k,total} = \tau \rho_k^p + (\tau_c - \tau) \rho_k^u$. Thus, the second component of the loss function penalizes the total energy constraint violation by adding a penalty to the loss when $E_{k,total} > E_{max}$. The set of coefficients λ_k are model hyperparameters and balances the trade-off between the sum rate objective and satisfying the total transmit energy constraints. This loss function is differentiable with $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ which allows training the network via stochastic gradient descent

(SGD). A mini-batch gradient descent approach is used in training to reduce the complexity of the SGD, where a set of channel realizations are generated from its distribution in each training iteration. The training loss is thus approximated as

$$loss \approx -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}|} \sum_{\boldsymbol{\beta} \in \mathcal{B}} \left[R(\boldsymbol{\beta}, \boldsymbol{\theta})_{sum} + \sum_{k=1}^K \lambda_k ReLU(E_{k,total} - E_{max}) \right], \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{B} denotes the set of channel realizations in each iteration and $|\mathcal{B}|$ is the mini-batch size. Thus, during training, the model learns parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ to minimize the loss given in (10) which maximizes the system sum rate. It is expected that the model converges to a suboptimal output upon model training which is close to the optimal solution to problem P1.

IV. SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

Here we present the numerical simulations to evaluate the performance of the proposed DL-based power control scheme in comparison with other heuristic and optimization-based power control approaches. We consider a cell-free MIMO system in a simulation area of $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ with different number of AP and user configurations. This square area is wrapped around at the edges to avoid boundary effects and to emulate a cell-free network with an infinite area [5]. Detailed simulation parameters are listed in Table I. The large-scale fading coefficient β_{mk} from k th user to m th AP is given by

$$\beta_{mk} = PL_{mk} 10^{\frac{\sigma_{sh} z_{mk}}{10}}, \quad (11)$$

where PL_{mk} is the pathloss from k th user to m th AP, calculated using the three-slope model used in [5] with parameters as in Table I. The shadow fading with standard deviation σ_{sh} , and $z_{mk} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is denoted by $10^{\frac{\sigma_{sh} z_{mk}}{10}}$. The noise power is $\sigma^2 = k_B \times T_0 \times \text{noise figure}$, where $k_B = 1.381 \times 10^{-23}$ Joule/Kelvin is the Boltzmann constant, $T_0 = 290$ Kelvin is the noise temperature, and noise figure = 9 dB.

A. Simulation Setup

A training dataset of 10^5 samples is used for model training. For each sample, different AP and user distributions were considered with randomly generated large-scale fading channel coefficients. Input to the DNN is normalized using the training dataset mean and variance. The network is trained for 200 iterations, using mini-batch gradient descent with $|\mathcal{B}| = 100$ samples using the ADAM optimizer with a learning rate of 0.005. After training, performance is evaluated for a different

TABLE I: Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Carrier frequency (f)	1.9 GHz
Simulation area length (D)	1 km
AP antenna height (h_{AP})	15 m
User antenna height (h_u)	1.65 m
d_0, d_1	10, 50 m
Bandwidth (B)	20 MHz
σ_{sh}	8 dB
Maximum energy per-user (E_{max})	200 mJ
Coherence interval (τ_c)	200 samples

test dataset consisting of 1000 samples where the trained model is used to produce the power allocation outputs and per-user rates are calculated using (7).

B. Results and Discussion

For performance comparison, we consider two scenarios with $M = 50, K = 10$ and $M = 100, K = 20$ APs and users randomly distributed over the $1 \times 1 \text{ km}^2$ simulation area. For the $K = 20$ case, both the orthogonal pilot assignment with $\tau = K = 20$ and random pilot assignment when $\tau = 10$ are used to evaluate the effect of power control when there is pilot contamination. We use two low-complexity heuristics based on equal power and energy allocation. For the equal energy allocation scheme, for each user, half of the total energy budget in a coherence interval is allocated to the pilot transmission, and the other half to the data transmission. Thus, $\rho_k^p = E_{max}/2\tau$ and $\rho_k^u = E_{max}/2(\tau_c - \tau) \quad \forall k$. For the equal power allocation scheme, we allocate fixed equal transmit powers for both pilots and data for each user, i.e., $\rho_k^p = \rho_k^u = E_{max}/\tau_c \quad \forall k$. Note that the energy spent for pilot and data transmission is not the same in the equal power allocation scheme. In both these schemes, the power allocations are fixed for all the users across all the channel realizations, and the full energy budget of E_{max} is used.

Fig. 1 shows the cumulative distribution curves for the sum rate for different power allocation strategies for the $M = 50, K = 10$ scenario with orthogonal pilot allocation. It can be seen that DL-based joint power control significantly improves the sum rate performance compared to the equal power allocation and equal energy allocation schemes. The ‘‘Data power control only’’ shows the performance when data power control is performed with $\rho_k^p = 100 \text{ mW}$ and $\rho_k^u \leq 100 \text{ mW}$ in each coherence interval, which results in around $100 \times$ higher energy consumption despite the improved sum rate.

Fig. 2 then illustrates the cumulative distribution curves for the sum rate in $M = 100, K = 20$ scenario with orthogonal pilot allocation and random pilot allocation with $\tau = 10$, respectively. In non-orthogonal pilots scenario, it can be seen that reduced signalling overhead and pilot power control help overcoming the sum rate degradation due to pilot contamination. Specifically, for the 90% likely sum rate, the DL-based power control resulted in 32.82% improvement for the orthogonal pilot case compared to the equal energy allocation and 29.22% improvement for the non-orthogonal

Fig. 1: Sum rate performance for $M = 50, K = 10$ with orthogonal pilots.

Fig. 2: Sum rate performance for $M = 100, K = 20$ with orthogonal and non-orthogonal pilots.

pilot case showing the impact of proper power control in the presence of pilot contamination.

Fig. 3 shows the pilot and data power distributions for $M = 100, K = 20$ with orthogonal and non-orthogonal pilot allocation for the test dataset with 1000 samples. While the data power coefficient distributions have not changed much, it can be seen that the pilot power is increased when using non-orthogonal pilots with $\tau = 10$, to overcome pilot contamination. Finally, Fig. 4 presents the average energy consumption for $M = 100, K = 20$. The equal power and equal energy schemes consume all the energy E_{max} . In contrast, the DNN-based power control results in significant energy savings by properly utilizing the pilot and data transmit powers. For $\tau = 20$ case, 63.35 % of the energy is saved while 59.06% is saved when $\tau = 10$. Thus, non-orthogonal pilot allocation has slightly increased the energy consumption as also seen from Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Histograms for pilot and data power coefficients for $M = 100$, $K = 20$ with orthogonal and non-orthogonal pilots.

Fig. 4: Average energy consumption for $M = 100$, $K = 20$ with orthogonal and non-orthogonal pilots.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed a DL-based algorithm for joint pilot and data power control for maximizing the uplink sum rate of a cell-free massive MIMO system. We extended the unsupervised learning approach in our previous work [16] to learn joint pilot and data power control under per-user total energy constraints. The proposed approach is shown to have a better sum rate performance and energy efficiency than the heuristic-based equal power and energy allocation schemes, and the optimization-based data power control only approach. Furthermore, the DL-based joint power allocation results in significant energy savings compared to the fixed power allo-

cation schemes. While we have obtained comparable results using a simple DNN model, the performance could be further improved by implementing better model architectures and further hyperparameter tuning. Furthermore, incorporating the access point selection to enable a user-centric cell-free network implementation is an important future research direction when considering the scalability of the proposed power control approach when the number of APs and users in the network increases.

REFERENCES

- [1] F. Boccardi, R. W. Heath, A. Lozano, T. L. Marzetta, and P. Popovski, "Five disruptive technology directions for 5G," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 74–80, 2014.
- [2] T. L. Marzetta, "Noncooperative cellular wireless with unlimited numbers of base station antennas," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 9, no. 11, pp. 3590–3600, 2010.
- [3] F. Rusek, D. Persson, B. K. Lau, E. G. Larsson, T. L. Marzetta, O. Edfors, and F. Tufvesson, "Scaling up MIMO: Opportunities and challenges with very large arrays," *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 40–60, 2013.
- [4] H. Q. Ngo, A. Ashikhmin, H. Yang, E. G. Larsson, and T. L. Marzetta, "Cell-free massive MIMO: Uniformly great service for everyone," in *2015 IEEE 16th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC)*, 2015, pp. 201–205.
- [5] H. Q. Ngo, A. Ashikhmin, H. Yang, E. G. Larsson, and T. L. Marzetta, "Cell-free massive MIMO versus small cells," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 1834–1850, 2017.
- [6] Y. Zhao, I. G. Niemegeers, and S. H. De Groot, "Power allocation in cell-free massive MIMO: A deep learning method," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 87 185–87 200, 2020.
- [7] T. C. Mai, H. Q. Ngo, M. Egan, and T. Q. Duong, "Pilot power control for cell-free massive mimo," *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 67, no. 11, pp. 11 264–11 268, 2018.
- [8] M. Sarker and A. O. Fapojuwo, "Pilot power allocation scheme for user-centric cell-free massive mimo systems," in *2023 IEEE 20th Consumer Communications and Networking Conference (CCNC)*, 2023, pp. 763–768.
- [9] G. Liu, H. Deng, X. Qian, W. Zhang, and H. Dong, "Joint pilot and data power control for cell-free massive mimo iot systems," *IEEE Sensors Journal*, vol. 22, no. 24, pp. 24 647–24 657, 2022.
- [10] I. M. Braga, R. P. Antonioli, G. Fodor, Y. C. B. Silva, and W. C. Freitas, "Joint pilot and data power control optimization in the uplink of user-centric cell-free systems," *IEEE Communications Letters*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 399–403, 2022.
- [11] H. Masoumi and M. J. Emadi, "Joint pilot and data power control in cell-free massive mimo system," in *2018 Fifth International Conference on Millimeter-Wave and Terahertz Technologies (MMWaTT)*, 2018, pp. 34–37.
- [12] L. Sanguinetti, A. Zappone, and M. Debbah, "Deep learning power allocation in massive MIMO," in *2018 52nd Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems, and Computers*, 2018, pp. 1257–1261.
- [13] C. D'Andrea, A. Zappone, S. Buzzi, and M. Debbah, "Uplink power control in cell-free massive MIMO via deep learning," in *2019 IEEE 8th International Workshop on Computational Advances in Multi-Sensor Adaptive Processing (CAMSAP)*, 2019, pp. 554–558.
- [14] F. Liang, C. Shen, W. Yu, and F. Wu, "Towards optimal power control via ensembling deep neural networks," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 1760–1776, 2020.
- [15] T. Van Chien, T. Nguyen Canh, E. Björnson, and E. G. Larsson, "Power control in cellular massive MIMO with varying user activity: A deep learning solution," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 5732–5748, 2020.
- [16] N. Rajapaksha, K. B. Shashika Manosha, N. Rajatheva, and M. Latva-Aho, "Deep learning-based power control for cell-free massive MIMO networks," in *ICC 2021 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*, 2021, pp. 1–7.
- [17] N. Rajapaksha, K. B. S. Manosha, N. Rajatheva, and M. Latva-aho, "Unsupervised learning-based joint power control and fronthaul capacity allocation in cell-free massive mimo with hardware impairments," *IEEE Wireless Communications Letters*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 1159–1163, 2023.